

1 Ecosystem shuffle: The `neutRal` R package to
2 simulate species dance moves

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7 **Abstract**

8 Understanding how biodiversity patterns emerge from simple eco-
9 logical processes remains a central challenge in community ecology.
10 Neutral theory provides a parsimonious framework in which species
11 are assumed to be ecologically equivalent and community dynamics
12 arise from stochastic processes such as dispersal, immigration, and
13 speciation. Despite its conceptual simplicity, the spatial implementa-
14 tion of neutral models is often computationally non-trivial and diffi-
15 cult to explore interactively.

16 In this paper I present `neutRal`, an R package designed to simulate
17 spatially explicit neutral community dynamics on a two-dimensional
18 lattice. The package implements a small set of transparent stochastic
19 rules governing local dispersal, global dispersal, and speciation, allow-
20 ing users to generate and visualize emergent spatial patterns and bio-
21 diversity gradients. `neutRal` provides a modular workflow consisting
22 of three core functions: simulation of neutral dynamics, visualization
23 of final spatial configurations, and calculation of biodiversity metrics
24 including species richness and Shannon diversity.

25 Through a series of simulation experiments, I illustrate how `neutRal`
26 can be used to check the influence of the key model parameters on the
27 achieved spatial patterns. By combining simplicity, reproducibility,
28 and spatial explicitness, `neutRal` offers an accessible platform for ex-
29 ploratory research, neutral model construction, and teaching in com-
30 putational ecology.

1 Introduction

Ecological communities are complex networks of species interacting with each other and their environment (Bazzichetto et al., 2018). These interactions include competition, predation, mutualism, and other processes that collectively determine the structure and dynamics of the community (Brown, 1995). The study of community ecology is essential for understanding biodiversity, ecosystem functioning, and the resilience of ecosystems to external pressures such as climate change, habitat destruction, and invasive species (Hooper et al., 2005; Amici et al., 2015).

Ecological modeling has become a fundamental tool for understanding the dynamics of ecological communities (Chiarucci et al., 2009). Models allow researchers to simulate complex ecological processes and test hypotheses that may be difficult or impossible to investigate empirically (Moudrý et al., 2024). One of the most valuable features of ecological modeling is the ability to simulate and explore scenarios in which environmental conditions or species interactions change, allowing for predictions about future community dynamics under various conditions (Grimm et al., 2005).

Among the different modelling frameworks in community ecology, neutral models have gained prominence as a mechanistic framework in which species are assumed to be ecologically equivalent and community dynamics emerge from stochastic demographic processes. (Gotelli, 2008). In such models, the dynamics of species spread are driven by random processes such as immigration, random birth and death events, and local dispersal (Leibold & McPeck, 2006). Neutral models offer a simple yet powerful framework for exploring patterns of biodiversity without requiring detailed information about the traits and interactions of species. Obviously, neutral models may not capture all aspects of community structure, but they might provide insights into how random processes and the balance between immigration and speciation can influence biodiversity over time (Hubbell, 2001). Moreover, they allow explicit control of key parameters, enabling hypothesis-driven tests on community assembly and comparisons with observed communities (Chave, 2004; Holyoak & Loreau, 2005).

Simulation approaches provide a practical way to explore the consequences of these neutral processes and to investigate how simple stochastic rules can generate complex biodiversity patterns. Running these models under a simulation framework provides ecologists with a deeper understanding of the fundamental processes driving species dynamics, especially in large-scale or long-term studies where direct observation is not feasible. For example, neutral models are particularly effective in exploring patterns of species distribution across vast landscapes, understanding the role of randomness in species

71 persistence, and investigating the long-term effects of immigration and spe-
72 ciation (Rosindell et al., 2012).

73 Furthermore, spatially explicit formulations of neutral models provide an
74 important extension of classical neutral theory by explicitly representing the
75 spatial arrangement of individuals and dispersal processes across landscapes
76 (Volkov et al., 2003). Such models allow researchers to investigate how local
77 dispersal, stochastic demographic events, and speciation interact to generate
78 spatial patterns of biodiversity, including spatial clustering, species turnover,
79 and dispersal limitation (Durrett & Levin, 1994; Chave & Leigh, 2002). By
80 explicitly incorporating space, these models make it possible to explore how
81 simple stochastic rules can give rise to complex spatial biodiversity patterns.

82 Despite the conceptual importance of neutral models, accessible tools for
83 exploring spatially explicit neutral dynamics remain limited. Many exist-
84 ing implementations focus on analytical formulations or require substantial
85 computational expertise. The aim of this paper is to introduce the `neutRal`
86 package, which provides a simple, transparent, and spatially explicit imple-
87 mentation of neutral community dynamics that integrates naturally within
88 the R ecosystem. Because R is widely used in ecological research for data
89 analysis, visualization, and reproducible workflows, the package facilitates
90 the exploration of neutral models within familiar analytical pipelines.

91 The specific aims of the `neutRal` package are: (i) to provide a simple
92 framework for simulating neutral species and community dynamics driven
93 by immigration, speciation, and local dispersal; (ii) to allow the exploration
94 of spatial patterns of species distributions under neutral assumptions; (iii)
95 to support the calculation and visualization of biodiversity metrics, such as
96 species richness and Shannon diversity, derived from simulated communities;
97 and, (iv) to offer an accessible tool for educators and researchers interested in
98 neutral theory, spatial ecology, and computational approaches to community
99 dynamics.

100 The package currently includes three primary functions designed to sim-
101 ulate spatially explicit neutral dynamics and to summarize and visualize
102 resulting biodiversity patterns. These functions allow users to model com-
103 munity dynamics on a grid-based landscape and to explore how stochastic
104 demographic processes influence species distributions over space and time. In
105 addition to the description of the theory and the algorithms of the package,
106 this paper presents example simulations demonstrating how `neutRal` can be
107 used to investigate species distributions and emergent biodiversity patterns
108 under neutral assumptions.

109 **2 Methods**

110 The `neutRal` package provides a concise framework for simulating and analysing
111 spatially explicit neutral community dynamics. The package is designed to
112 be simple and accessible for both researchers and educators in computational
113 ecology, allowing users to explore the emergence of biodiversity patterns un-
114 der neutral assumptions.

115 As previously stated, the package is composed of three core functions:

- 116 • `simulate_neutral_grid()` — Simulates the dynamics of a spatially
117 explicit neutral community on a two-dimensional lattice, generating a
118 grid of species identities after a specified number of simulation steps.
- 119 • `plot_neutral_grid()` — Based on the `ggplot2` package, it visualizes
120 the final spatial configuration of the neutral community by mapping
121 species identities across the lattice.
- 122 • `calculate_diversity()` — Computes biodiversity metrics, including
123 species richness, total number of individuals, and Shannon diversity,
124 from the simulated grid.

125 **2.1 Installation**

126 To get the `neutRal` package, one can use the `devtools` package to install it
127 directly from GitHub, as:

```
128 devtools::install_github("ducciorocchini/neutRal")
```

129 **2.2 Functions**

130 **2.2.1 Spatially explicit neutral community simulation by the** 131 **`simulate_neutral_grid()` function**

132 The `simulate_neutral_grid()` function simulates spatially explicit neutral
133 community dynamics on an $n \times n$ grid over a specified number of time steps.
134 A time step in the function corresponds to a single stochastic update event
135 (i.e., a death–replacement event) affecting one randomly selected cell, and
136 does not represent a fixed ecological time unit such as a year or generation.

137 The grid is initialized with unique species identities in each cell (maximal
138 diversity), and community composition changes through stochastic replace-
139 ment events. At each time step, a randomly selected cell is updated either
140 through local dispersal, by copying the species identity of a randomly chosen
141 von Neumann neighbor (von Neumann, 1951), or through an immigration

142 event. A von Neumann neighborhood is defined as the set of four orthog-
143 onally adjacent cells (up, down, left, and right) surrounding a focal cell on
144 the lattice. During immigration events, a new species can be introduced
145 with probability ν , representing speciation. Optionally, the function allows
146 storing snapshots of the grid at user-defined time intervals.

147 Because the grid is initialized with arbitrary species identities (maximal
148 initial diversity), the early phase of the simulation may reflect transient dy-
149 namics that depend on the initial configuration. Over time, the community
150 approaches a stochastic dynamical equilibrium that is independent of these
151 initial conditions. In practice, it is good practice to allow a burn-in phase
152 before analysing the simulated community. Convergence toward equilibrium
153 can be assessed by monitoring summary statistics such as species richness and
154 Shannon diversity, which are implemented in the `calculate_diversity()`
155 function.

156 Each update event represents a death-replacement process in which the
157 individual occupying the focal cell dies and is immediately replaced either
158 by local dispersal from a neighbouring cell, by immigration, or by specia-
159 tion. This update rule corresponds to a spatially explicit implementation of
160 a Moran-type stochastic process, a standard formulation used in neutral com-
161 munity models (Moran, 1958). The model follows a zero-sum assumption,
162 where the total number of individuals in the community remains constant
163 (Etienne, 2007; Haegeman & Etienne, 2008).

164 The key features of the simulation are: (i) immigration events, which oc-
165 cur with probability m and replace the species identity at a randomly chosen
166 cell by drawing an identity from the current grid (global sampling) - in the
167 current implementation, immigration events correspond to global sampling
168 from the existing community, representing long-distance dispersal within the
169 landscape rather than colonization from an external metacommunity; (ii)
170 speciation, which occurs during immigration events with probability ν and
171 introduces a novel species identity; and (iii) local dispersal, which occurs oth-
172 erwise and updates the focal cell by copying the species identity of a randomly
173 chosen von Neumann neighbor (up, down, left, right) with periodic (wrap-
174 around) boundaries. The simulation is carried out over a specified number
175 of time steps, with the grid updated at each step. The output includes the
176 final grid representing the spatial distribution of species (algorithm 1). At
177 each time step, a random number is drawn from a uniform distribution to
178 determine whether a global dispersal event occurs with probability m ; oth-
179 erwise, local dispersal is applied. Conditional on a global dispersal event, a
180 second random draw determines whether speciation occurs with probability
181 ν .

Algorithm 1 Algorithm for `simulate_neutral_grid()`

```
1: Set the random seed to seed.
2: Initialize an  $n \times n$  grid with a unique species identifier in each cell
   (maximal diversity).
3: Set next_species_id to  $n^2 + 1$ .
4: Initialize empty containers: snapshots and snapshot_steps.
5: for each time step  $t$  from 1 to steps do
6:   Randomly select a cell  $(i, j)$  on the grid.
7:   if a global dispersal (immigration) event occurs with probability  $m$ 
   then
8:     if a speciation event occurs with probability  $\nu$  then
9:       Assign species next_species_id to cell  $(i, j)$ .
10:      Increment next_species_id by 1.
11:    else
12:      Replace the species in cell  $(i, j)$  by sampling a species identity
   at random from the current grid (immigration from the local pool).
13:    end if
14:  else
15:    Select a random von Neumann neighbor  $(i', j')$  of  $(i, j)$  using pe-
   riodic boundary conditions.
16:    Replace the species in cell  $(i, j)$  with the species identity found in
   the neighboring cell  $(i', j')$  (local dispersal).
17:  end if
18:  if snapshot_every is not NULL and  $t$  is a multiple of snapshot_every
   then
19:    Append the current grid to snapshots.
20:    Append  $t$  to snapshot_steps.
21:  end if
22: end for
23: Return a list containing: the final grid (grid), optional snapshots
   (snapshots), the corresponding time steps (snapshot_steps), and the
   simulation parameters (params).
```

182 In practice, the algorithm works as follows:

183 1. **Initialization:** The random seed is set to ensure reproducibility. The
184 landscape is represented as an $n \times n$ lattice in which each cell initially
185 contains a unique species identifier, corresponding to maximal initial
186 diversity. The variable `next_species_id` is set to $n^2 + 1$ and is used to
187 assign unique identifiers to newly speciated lineages.

- 188 2. **Iterative dynamics:** The model is updated for a total of `steps` it-
 189 erations. At each iteration, a single cell (i, j) is selected uniformly at
 190 random and updated according to either an immigration event (with
 191 possible speciation) or a local dispersal event.
- 192 3. **Immigration and speciation:** With probability m , the selected cell
 193 undergoes an immigration event.
- 194 • Conditional on immigration, with probability ν , a speciation event
 195 occurs and the selected cell is assigned a new, unique species identi-
 196 fier (`next_species_id`), which is then incremented.
 - 197 • Otherwise, the selected cell is assigned a species identity sampled
 198 uniformly at random from all cells in the current grid, representing
 199 a global draw from the species already present in the simulated
 200 landscape.
- 201 4. **Local dispersal:** With probability $1 - m$, the selected cell is updated
 202 via local dispersal. A von Neumann neighbor (up, down, left, or right)
 203 is chosen at random using periodic boundary conditions (wrap-around
 204 at the grid edges), and the species identity of the neighboring cell is
 205 copied into the focal cell.
- 206 5. **Optional snapshots:** If `snapshot_every` is provided, intermediate
 207 community states are recorded by storing a copy of the grid every
 208 `snapshot_every` iterations, together with the corresponding iteration
 209 index. These snapshots allow reconstruction of temporal trajectories
 210 without embedding any visualization routines within the simulation.
- 211 6. **Final output:** After all iterations are completed, the function returns
 212 a list containing the final grid (representing the spatial configuration
 213 of species identities), any recorded snapshots and their associated time
 214 steps, and the parameter set used in the simulation.

215 To illustrate the use of the algorithm in practice, the following code runs a
 216 spatially explicit neutral community simulation using the `simulate_neutral_grid()`
 217 function:

```
218 # Run simulation
219 sim <- simulate_neutral_grid(
220   n = 80,
221   steps = 200000,
222   m = 0.01,
```

```
223   nu = 0.001,  
224   seed = 1  
225 )
```

226 This example generates a neutral community on an 80×80 lattice by
227 iteratively updating the grid for 200,000 steps. At each step, the species
228 identity of a randomly selected cell is replaced according to neutral dynamics.

229 The parameter $m = 0.01$ defines the probability of an immigration event,
230 while $nu = 0.001$ specifies the probability of speciation conditional on immi-
231 gration. The random seed is fixed (`seed = 1`) to ensure that the simulation
232 is fully reproducible.

233 The resulting object `sim` is a list containing the final spatial configuration
234 of species identities across the grid, together with the parameter values used
235 in the simulation. This output can subsequently be used for visualization (by
236 the `plot_neutral_grid()` function, subsection 2.2.2) and for the calculation
237 of biodiversity metrics (by the `calculate_diversity()` function, subsection
238 2.2.3).

239 2.2.2 Visualization of simulated neutral communities by the 240 `plot_neutral_grid()` function

241 The function `plot_neutral_grid()` provides a graphical representation of
242 the spatial configuration of individuals generated by the neutral model. The
243 community is visualized as a two-dimensional grid in which each cell corre-
244 sponds to an individual and is coloured according to its species identity.

245 The input matrix `grid` represents the final state of the simulated commu-
246 nity, with integer values identifying species, inherited from the preceding call
247 to the `simulate_neutral_grid()` function, together with the other parame-
248 ters: the number of cells n (`params$n`) along each side of the square lattice,
249 the number of steps (`params$steps`), the dispersal probability m (`params$m`)
250 and the speciation rate ν (`params$nu`). The simulation parameters are not
251 required to generate the plot, but are used exclusively to add informative
252 text describing the simulation settings in the final graph. In other words,
253 the simulation parameters in the `plot_neutral_grid()` function serve an
254 annotational purpose rather than a computational one.

255 Internally, the function converts the simulated grid into a data frame
256 suitable for visualization by expanding the spatial coordinates and associat-
257 ing each cell with its corresponding species identifier. Species identifiers are
258 treated as categorical variables to ensure discrete colour mapping. The spa-
259 tial layout is rendered using a raster-based approach, preserving the square
260 geometry of the lattice.

261 The function can be applied directly to the output of `simulate_neutral_grid()`,
262 using the associated simulation parameters to annotate the visualization, as
263 shown below:

```
264 # Plot final community state
265 plot_neutral_grid(
266   grid = sim$grid,
267   n     = sim$params$n,
268   steps = sim$params$steps,
269   m     = sim$params$m,
270   nu    = sim$params$nu
271 )
```

272 The resulting plot displays the spatial mosaic of species across the grid
273 (Figure 1), enabling rapid qualitative assessment of spatial clustering, rela-
274 tive prevalence, and patchiness emerging from neutral dynamics. To empha-
275 size spatial structure rather than individual species identities, the legend is
276 intentionally suppressed.

Figure 1: Species spread on a grid over multiple time steps. Each color represents a different species.

277 **2.2.3 Calculation of biodiversity metrics by the `calculate_diversity()`**
 278 **function**

279 The `calculate_diversity()` function computes basic biodiversity metrics
 280 from the simulated community grid, including species richness (S), the total
 281 number of individuals (N), and Shannon diversity (H'), by:

```
282 # Calculate biodiversity metrics
283 calculate_diversity(sim$grid)
```

284 Using the simulated community generated in the previous example, $S =$
 285 313, $N = 6400$ (namely the squared number of pixels), $H' = 5.443$.

286 **3 Example simulations using the neutRal pack-** 287 **age**

288 This section provides simple illustrative simulations to demonstrate how the
289 `neutRal` package can be used to explore spatial neutral community dynamics.
290 These examples are intended solely as a practical demonstration of the pack-
291 age functionality rather than as a comprehensive ecological analysis. The link
292 to the complete code is provided in the “Data and code availability” section
293 below (section 6). As previously stated, in spatially explicit neutral models,
294 community dynamics are typically represented as the outcome of stochastic
295 processes with two key parameters like the immigration probability (m) -
296 influencing the degree of spatial mixing observed in the community - and
297 the speciation probability (ν) - controlling the probability that a speciation
298 event occurs during immigration.

299 To illustrate how these parameters affect simulated communities, I gener-
300 ated a set of spatial neutral simulations and visualized their final community
301 configurations in Figure 2, arranged in a 2×2 layout. In the top row, only
302 the immigration probability m is varied while the speciation probability ν is
303 held constant. In the bottom row, only the speciation probability ν is varied
304 while m is held constant. All simulations correspond to the terminal state of
305 an 80×80 lattice after 200,000 update steps.

306 Importantly, ν does not directly affect dispersal or replacement mecha-
307 nisms and therefore tends to have a comparatively weaker influence on the
308 resulting spatial configurations (Figure 2, bottom row).

Figure 2: Final spatial configurations of neutral communities under different values of immigration probability (m) and speciation probability (ν). The top row shows the effect of varying m with ν held constant, whereas the bottom row shows the effect of varying ν with m held constant. For each panel, species richness (S) and Shannon diversity (H') are reported.

309 On the contrary, in these illustrative simulations increasing m (top row)
310 results in greater spatial mixing and reduced persistence of large, contiguous
311 patches formed by local dispersal. As expected, these illustrative simula-
312 tions suggest that, within the parameter ranges explored here, immigration
313 strongly influences the spatial structure of the simulated community, whereas
314 speciation has a more limited effect on the final spatial configuration.

315 4 Discussion

316 The results presented in this paper demonstrate how a small set of stochastic
317 rules governing dispersal, immigration, and speciation can generate complex
318 spatial patterns, even in the absence of species-specific traits or explicit en-
319 vironmental heterogeneity.

320 A central result emerging from the simulations concerns the distinct roles
321 of immigration (m) and speciation (ν). Varying m primarily affects the
322 spatial organization of the community, altering the degree of clustering and
323 the persistence of spatial autocorrelation generated by local dispersal. In
324 contrast, varying ν exerts a comparatively weak effect on large-scale spatial
325 patterns of species distribution (Chave & Leigh, 2002; Rosindell & Phillimore,
326 2011). The explicit spatial implementation in `neutRai` makes this theoretical
327 result immediately visible and quantifiable.

328 From a methodological perspective, `neutRai` occupies a specific niche
329 among ecological modelling tools available in R. Several packages implement
330 neutral or stochastic community models, including `vegan`, `untb`, `EcoSimR`,
331 and `spatstat`. Other spatially explicit community simulation frameworks
332 have also been developed, including the neutral simulator in C++ by (Rosin-
333 dell et al., 2008), the `MCSim` package (Sokol et al., 2017), the simulation
334 metacommunity framework proposed by Jabot et al. (2020) and its exten-
335 sion to spatial connectivity by (Jacquet et al., 2022), the Julia implemen-
336 tation by Suzuki & Economo (2021), or broader spatial ecological modelling
337 frameworks such as the Overview, Design concepts, and Details (ODD) pro-
338 tocol (Grimm et al., 2010), mechanistic simulation models (Cabral, 2017),
339 agent-based platforms such as NetLogo (see e.g., (Wilensky & Rand, 2015;
340 Railsback & Grimm, 2019)). Such tools have proven extremely valuable and
341 provide flexible environments for exploring spatial ecological dynamics, offer-
342 ing advanced simulation capabilities. This is particularly useful for exploring
343 neutral theory, neutral model testing, and spatial point pattern analysis.
344 However, such modeling frameworks might require a relatively high level of
345 theoretical or computational expertise.

346 On the contrary, the primary goal of the `neutRai` package is to provide

347 an easily modifiable spatial neutral model within the R ecosystem, facilitat-
348 ing integration with existing ecological analysis and visualization tools. In
349 practice, `neutRal` emphasizes simplicity, transparency, and pedagogical clar-
350 ity. The model is fully specified by a small number of intuitive parameters,
351 and the state of the system is explicitly represented as a two-dimensional
352 lattice. This design choice facilitates direct inspection of the simulated com-
353 munity, making it easier to link stochastic rules to emergent patterns. While
354 this simplicity inevitably limits the range of ecological processes that can be
355 represented, it is also one of the main strengths of the package. By low-
356 ering the conceptual and technical barrier to entry, `neutRal` makes spatial
357 neutral modelling accessible to a broader audience, including students and
358 researchers new to computational ecology.

359 Another distinguishing feature of `neutRal` is its explicit separation be-
360 tween simulation, visualization, and analysis. The simulation function re-
361 turns the full grid state without embedding any plotting or summary statis-
362 tics. Visualization and diversity calculation are handled by separate func-
363 tions, which operate directly on the simulation output. This modular struc-
364 ture improves reproducibility and extensibility, allowing users to integrate
365 `neutRal` into larger workflows or to replace individual components with cus-
366 tomized alternatives. For example, the output grid can be readily used as
367 input for additional spatial analyses, comparison with empirical data, or cou-
368 pling with environmental layers.

369 Although the present paper focuses on neutral dynamics, the framework
370 implemented in `neutRal` also provides a useful baseline for exploring depart-
371 ures from neutrality. Neutral models are often most informative when used
372 as basic expectations against which more complex processes can be evalu-
373 ated (Chave, 2004). In this sense, `neutRal` can serve as a reference model
374 for assessing the added explanatory power of niche differentiation, competi-
375 tive asymmetries, environmental filtering, or adaptive evolution. By starting
376 from a well-defined neutral baseline, researchers can more clearly identify
377 which patterns require non-neutral explanations (McGill, 2003).

378 The educational value of `neutRal` should also be emphasized. Spatially
379 explicit neutral models are frequently discussed in theoretical ecology, yet
380 their implications are not always intuitive. The ability to interactively mod-
381 ify parameters such as m and ν and immediately visualize their effects can
382 substantially enhance understanding of core ecological concepts, including
383 dispersal limitation, turnover, and the stochastic nature of biodiversity. In
384 teaching contexts, `neutRal` can therefore function as a bridge between ab-
385 stract theory and tangible spatial outcomes.

386 Despite its advantages, some limitations of the current implementation
387 should be acknowledged. First, the lattice-based representation assumes ho-

388 homogeneous space and periodic boundary conditions, which may not be appro-
389 priate for all ecological systems (Grimm et al., 2005). Second, all individuals
390 are treated as ecologically equivalent, and no explicit environmental gradients
391 or habitat preferences are included (see (Bacaro, 2015) on the effect of ecolog-
392 ical gradients on distributional patterns). These simplifications are inherent
393 to neutral theory (Caswell, 1976; Bell, 2000, 2001), but they also constrain
394 the range of ecological questions that can be addressed. Users should there-
395 fore interpret the results of `neutRal` as exploratory or hypothesis-generating
396 rather than predictive.

397 Future developments of the package could proceed along several direc-
398 tions. One natural extension would be the inclusion of spatial heterogeneity
399 (sensu (Palmer, 2007; Anderle et al., 2023)), for example by allowing dispersal
400 probabilities or immigration rates to vary across the grid (Chase & Leibold ,
401 2009). Another promising avenue would be the incorporation of weak niche
402 differences or fitness asymmetries, thereby enabling systematic exploration of
403 the continuum between neutral and niche- based dynamics (Chesson, 2000;
404 Adler et al., 2007; Chase & Myers, 2002). Additionally, tighter integration
405 with spatial data formats and raster objects would facilitate comparisons
406 between simulated and empirical landscapes.

407 Another simplification of the current implementation is that the model
408 does not include a distinct regional species pool (metacommunity) from which
409 immigrants originate, as in Hubbell’s original neutral theory (Hubbell, 2001).
410 Instead, immigration events correspond to global sampling from the existing
411 simulated community. This choice was made to keep the algorithm and its
412 implementation simple and straightforward. However, the absence of an ex-
413 plicit regional pool removes an important feature of classical neutral models,
414 namely the separation of time scales between local and regional dynamics. In
415 models with a metacommunity, species abundance dynamics at the regional
416 scale tend to evolve more slowly than local community dynamics, which can
417 buffer local fluctuations through immigration processes, particularly when
418 community size becomes large. A further step in the development of the
419 package could extend the current framework to include an explicit metacom-
420 munity component.

421 **5 Conclusion**

422 The `neutRal` package provides a compact framework for exploring spatially
423 explicit neutral community dynamics in R. By being released as open-source
424 software, it supports reproducibility, scrutiny, and long-term reuse: users
425 can inspect the underlying assumptions, verify results, and adapt the code

426 to their own systems and teaching needs (Rocchini et al., 2021; von Hard-
427 enberg, 2025; Uyen et al., 2025). Open development also encourages com-
428 munity contributions, including bug fixes, performance improvements, and
429 extensions to new ecological scenarios, thereby increasing the reliability and
430 longevity of the tool (Rocchini & Neteler, 2012). In this sense, `neutRal` is not
431 only a simulator but also a shareable and modifiable reference implementa-
432 tion that lowers barriers to entry for spatial neutral modelling and facilitates
433 comparisons across studies.

434 At the modelling level, the package relies on a deliberately small set of
435 stochastic rules governing local dispersal, immigration, and speciation. This
436 parsimonious design allows users to investigate how complex spatial patterns
437 and biodiversity gradients can emerge in the absence of species-specific traits
438 or explicit environmental heterogeneity. The results presented in this study
439 confirm that even minimal neutral assumptions are sufficient to generate rich
440 and interpretable ecological outcomes when embedded in a spatial context.

441 **6 Data and code availability**

442 All simulations and figures presented in this study were generated using
443 the `neutRal` R package. The package is available on GitHub at [https://](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/neutRal)
444 github.com/ducciorocchini/neutRal (development version) and perma-
445 nently archived on Zenodo with DOI at [https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19030070)
446 [19030070](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19030070).

447 All simulations and figures presented in this paper are fully reproducible
448 using the example code distributed with the package. The scripts used to re-
449 produce the analyses and visualizations are provided in the package documen-
450 tation and example files located at [https://github.com/ducciorocchini/](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/neutRal/tree/main/man)
451 [neutRal/tree/main/man](https://github.com/ducciorocchini/neutRal/tree/main/man).

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